

Goal Setting Among Adolescents in Relation to Parental Involvement

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ABSTRACT: Background: Goal setting is an incredible strategy or instrument for assisting understudies with giving a strong establishment to upgrading their presentation. By understanding what he/she needs to accomplish throughout everyday life, understudies/youths may know where they need to think and what is to improve. On the off chance that teenagers/understudies can set very much characterized objectives, they can gauge and invest wholeheartedly in the accomplishment of those objectives. The main undertaking before an educator or instructor or parent is to help the understudies in defining transient objectives and long haul objectives. Objective setting gives self-assurance and inspiration to the understudy which is a fundamental key to improve or raise execution. Goal setting is a psychological cycle that includes setting up of explicit destinations, estimations and methodology to accomplish the objective, which likewise remembers the technique alteration for terms of the input or blunder made. The main objective of the study was to examine goal setting among adolescents in relation to parental involvement. To accomplish the objective, Goal Setting Scale developed by the investigator and Parental Involvement Scale by Dr. Sangeeta Tramma, 1998 were adopted.

Materials and methods: The descriptive survey method was employed for the present investigation. The sample consists of 464 adolescents studied in CBSE affiliated schools of Ludhiana district of Punjab. Data has been collected from students of 9th and 10th class whose parents are graduates or undergraduates. The sample was further categorized into male and female students. Sample has been drawn by employing simple random sampling technique, Stratified random sampling technique, purposive sampling technique and systematic random sampling technique.

Results: Findings of the study reveal significant relationship between goal setting among adolescents and dimensions of parental involvement; significant relationship between goal setting among male adolescents and dimensions of parental involvement and significant relationship between goal setting among female adolescents and dimensions of parental involvement.

Conclusion: The study has practical implications for students to set goals before doing any educational and vocational tasks or activities; study also has practical implications for parents to provide such environment that will help their child in setting goals and it will also helpful for teachers and educational administrators in organizing such activities and programmes that ensures parent's involvement in their child's goal setting.

KEYWORDS: Goal Setting, Parental Involvement, Adolescents.

I. INTRODUCTION

Goal setting are crucial to human fulfillment and achievements in special areas of lifestyles. Goals act like a driving force which assists a character to continue within the hardest situations. An adolescent who appears to be a carrier of massive obligation on his shoulders can't be successful in his life till and except sets goals for himself. An individual who set goals earlier than doing any vital mission will routinely improve his overall performance due to the fact the ones goals continually direct him to stroll on that line and make him centered. Setting of goals proved to be foundation stone of taking effective decision toward actualization of the set desires. Goals have terrific contribution in success, efficiency or overall performance of an individual. Children of today are the future of the next day so; they must set their goals before doing any pastime or getting to know mission or deciding on career. To boom overall performance in any field whether it is instructional or vocational one must be deliberate and nicely guided. But aspect is to set realistic goals. Beginners who set practical dreams can be greater inspired than the ones newbie's who set unachievable goals (Ipaye, 2007).

Whilst students set their personal goals, they take duty and controller in their learning desires. Such goal directed behaviour that end result from goal placing is empowering and proactive (Elliot & Fryer, 2008). Placing practical and more practical goals ends in excellence but we cannot forget this truth that every person is not successful or mature enough for placing goal for him or taking right decision especially a teen due to the fact a teen is going through many physiological and psychological modifications at this

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stage. A teenager is underneath strain and pressure and sometime cannot take proper choice for him or we can say that no longer capable of set desires for himself. Parents are the second God on the planet. Parent's involvement, their encouragement, aspirations, expectations and guidance work as a panacea for his or her child. A knowledgeable and involved figure can higher manual their baby in placing dreams.

Goal

A goal is the aim or object toward which an endeavour is directed. While a pupil sets a goal it proved to be a key factor in attaining achievement or enhance performance. For scholar a goal includes accomplishing centered rankings, marks, grades, progressing in skills and retaining motivation at some point of. The word goal has been defined as the object to which effort or ambition is directed; the destination of a adventure . . . An stop or result in the direction of which behaviour is consciously or unconsciously directed (Oxford English Dictionary, 2010). To set a goal is to plan for the future, to recognize a certain nation of being; it entails conscious behavioural goal that channels our energies or motivation to help us reap future targets (Muchinsky, 2000). In addition goal setting serves as a guide and evokes attempt towards development. Goals are defined because the cease in the direction of which attempt is directed (Webster Dictionary, 1995). A purpose is the goal of a movement or task that a person consciously wants to obtain or obtain (Locke & Latham, 2002; Locke & Latham, 2006).

Types of Goals

Goals are typically break down into corporations: "mastery" or "getting to know" dreams and "overall performance" goals. Mastery dreams contain displaying information, abilities, and content information while overall performance goals then again contain achieving a pre-described overall performance degree or outperforming others. Researchers have reliably located that understudies who have a mastery goal outlook display in addition mental system, plan the entire extra correctly, and are steadily versatile to challenges. Performance focused understudies show an increasing number of unfavorable effects to disappointment, see lesser connection among exertion and result, and more spotlight on their presentation comparative with the exhibition of others (Pintrich, 2003; Seifert, 2004). Subsequently from mental factor of view mastery desires have greater effect or they are more powerful than performance goals. The 2 college students can have different standpoint concerning goals in specific contexts, however; he or she may additionally have mastery in a single state of affairs and a performance in other. Researchers along with Bandura (1986) and Locke and Latham (1990 and 2002) have recognized specific goals properties and have explored how diverse goals interface with accomplishment outcomes. Elliot and Sheldon (1997) characterize four types of goals: (1) task-explicit goals for execution, as an instance, "Make this unfastened toss"; (2) circumstance explicit goals, for instance, "display my capability comparative with others in this condition"; (3) personal goals, for example, "Get passing marks"; and (4) self-standards goals for destiny conditions, for instance, "a while or another I might be a university alum".

Parental Involvement

A number of phrases and meanings were used to describe and explain the involvement of parents, and parental involvement is constantly felt a subject of studies and dialogue in youngsters' academic consequences. The phrases "Parental Engagement", "Parental Involvement", "Parental Advocacy" and "Parental representation" are some of the most commonly used expression; however researchers have unique views on what each of those surely mean. These terms are frequently used interchangeably and may have distinct meaning in different contexts.

Parental involvement is defined because the teacher's notion of the high-quality attitude of mother and father towards their child's education, instructor, and school (Webster-Stratton, 1998). Parental involvement in schooling as parental behaviour with, or on behalf of kids, at domestic or at school, in addition to the expectancies that father and mother hold for youngster's future education (Berthelsen and Walker, 2008).

Hoover, Kathleen and Sandler wrote article on parent involvement in children's training: Why does it make a difference? Which turned into posted in 1995 defined parental involvement broadly to encompass domestic-based totally sports (e.g., supporting with homework, discussing college occasions or guides) and faculty-based activities (e.g., volunteering at faculty, coming to high school activities). They opined that parental involvement is a fabricated from a determine beliefs approximately their roles and obligations, a figure's experience that they can assist her kids reach school, and the possibilities for involvement supplied by using the school or instructor. They similarly explored whilst parents get worried, child's training or success is affected through their acquisition of information, capabilities, and through confidence. Peters (2012) said that on the point whilst colleges have received notoriety for being fruitful, they for the most component have loads of dedication from guardians. (Nihat, Sad& Gurbuzturk 2013) mentioned that accomplishment at faculty is ensured if college-primarily based steering is bolstered with the aid of guardians' inclusion at domestic. Inclusive of guardians in education has been stated to yield fine outcomes in numerous regards consisting of pupil participation, higher scholarly accomplishment, notion, faculty connection, responsibility and certainty, better social adjustment and much less order troubles. Consistent with Sapungan and Sapungan (2014) if we consist of the guardians in education in their youngsters, it deserves saying that the faculty is proactive in actualizing modifications or advancement among the college students. As parent's association is expanded nature of guidance may be advanced.

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By analyzing the studies associated with goal setting and parental involvement, the researcher has come to the conclusion that there is no observe at once link with the goal setting and parental involvement amongst youth in the subject of education. They are associated with parental assist or parental involvement or parental impacts, parenting patterns, own family structure and function of own family in profession picks, profession choices, and occupational aspirations as concluded from the studies of Hairston, 2000; Taylor, Harris and Taylor, 2004; Dietrich and Salmela-Aro, 2013. Look at of Baharudin, Hong and Zulkefly, 2010 suggests there may be courting among parenting practices and academic purpose of unmarried father and unmarried mother while observe of Ruholt, Gore and Dukes, 2015 showed association between parental involvement and academic self-efficacy or academic well-being. Researcher similarly concluded that once mother and father are supportive and actively concerned of their adolescent's lifestyles and training they feel much less stress at home and feature a tremendous attitude closer to college as indicated from the have a look at of Brown and Iyengar, 2008. It has additionally been concluded by way of the investigator that father became greater associated in profession related desires than moms as supported by means of Tynkkynen (2013).

Objectives

1. To find out the relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
2. To find out the relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
3. To find out the relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).

Hypotheses

1. There exists significant relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
2. There exists significant relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).
3. There exists significant relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour).

II. RESEARCH DESIGN

Inside the current research, a quantitative, descriptive and correlation survey method was employed. The main objective of the look at was to take a look at the intention amongst young people in terms of Parental Involvement. The studies method used inside the present examine is quantitative as this approach of studies is used to quantify the hassle with the aid of generating numerical records that may be converted into useable facts.

Target Population

In the present research population constituted the students of 9th and 10th studying in C.B.S.E. affiliated public schools of Ludhiana district of Punjab has been taken. However, due to huge size of population, researchers regularly cannot test every man or woman in the population because it's miles too steeply-priced and time consuming. That is why researcher is predicated on sampling strategies.

Procedure

A previous appointment was fixed with school authorities after decided on aforementioned (schools of Ludhiana district) to apprise them of the objectives of the present study and to achieve their permission for statistics series. A tentative time table for facts series changed into then organized in discussion with the authorities. Records were acquired after sharing the objectives of the examination and reassuring the participants approximately their anonymity and the confidentiality of facts they could be imparting. Data became amassed with the assist of Goal Setting Scale developed by the investigator and Parental Involvement Scale by Tramma, 1998. The tools used to acquire facts have been administrated in one session. To ensure genuineness of the records, investigator requested the students to be honest in giving responses. Enough time become given to allow the students to complete their paintings at his/ her convenience. After the test turned into over, sheets were accrued and the records changed into statistically analyzed.

Sample and Sampling Method

Within the present study simple random sampling approach, stratified random sampling technique, systematic random sampling method and purposive sampling strategies had been adopted. Initially, list of the public schools affiliated to C.B.S.E. changed into downloaded from website (www.justdial.com). There were 188 colleges in wide variety. After that 10 schools were decided on by using lottery technique of easy random sampling technique. By employing purposive sampling technique the researcher selected adolescents on the basis of educational qualification of the father and mother (graduate or under-graduate). After that a list was organized on the basis of gender. For the reason that goal of the researcher was to acquire a sample of 464 adolescents. Stratified random sampling technique and systematic random sampling changed into used to select the favored quantity of sample.

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Tools Used for Data Collection

- Goal Setting Scale was developed by the investigator.
- Parental Involvement Scale by Tramma (1998).

Statistical Techniques Employed

Karl Pearson coefficient of Correlation was employed to see the relationship between the variables under study.

III. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Table 1: Coefficient of Correlation between Goal Setting among Adolescents and Dimensions of Parental Involvement

Variables	Category	N	r	Sig./Not Sig.
Goal Setting and Personal Involvement	Adolescents	464	0.34	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Cognitive Stimulation	Adolescents	464	0.32	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Behaviour Involvement	Adolescents	464	-0.24	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Cognitive Behaviour	Adolescents	464	0.16	Sig. at .01

Table 1 shows that

- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.34 which is significant at 0.01 level. Table further shows that there exist a positive relationship between Goal setting among adolescents and dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.32 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exist a positive relationship between Goal setting among adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is -0.24 which is significant at 0.01 level which shows that there exist negative relationship between Goal setting among adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.16 which is significant at 0.01 level which shows that there exist positive relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

Therefore hypothesis 1 stating that “There exists significant relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour),” stands accepted. The findings of the study are in consistent with the result of Baharudin, Hong and Zulkefly, 2010 that shows there is relationship between parenting practices and educational goal of single father and single mother; study of Ruholt, Gore and Dukes, 2015 shows association between parental involvement and academic self-efficacy or academic well-being.

Results further indicate that personal involvement of parents i.e. affective and emotional experiences towards their child, their involvement in academics and social life of the child; Cognitive stimulation to adolescents thoughts and feelings and cognitive behaviour of parents like reading books, magazines, newspaper etc. are positively correlated with goal setting of adolescents which means that more parental involvement leads to more goal setting among adolescents as far as the behaviour involvement of parents is concerned i.e. going to the child’s school, meetings his teachers, attending parent-teacher meetings is negatively correlated with goal setting of adolescents which means that more behaviour involvement of parents leads to less goal settings among adolescents.

Table 2: Coefficient of Correlation between Goal Setting among Male adolescents and Dimensions of Parental Involvement

Variables	Category	N	r	Sig./Not Sig.
Goal Setting and Personal Involvement	Male adolescents	232	0.31	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Cognitive Stimulation	Male Adolescents	232	0.27	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Behaviour Involvement	Male Adolescents	232	-0.21	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Cognitive Behaviour	Male adolescents	232	0.18	Sig. at .01

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Table 2 shows that

- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.31 which is significant at 0.01 level. Table further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.27 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is -0.21 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exists negative relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.18 which is significant at 0.01 level which shows that there exist positive relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

Therefore hypothesis 2 stating that “There exists significant relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour),” stands accepted.

Results further explore that parents personal involvement, their cognitive stimulation to adolescents thoughts and feelings and Cognitive Behaviour is positively correlated with Goal Setting among male adolescents which means that more personal involvement of parents, more cognitive stimulation and their cognitive behaviour leads to more goal setting among male adolescents; as far as the behaviour involvement of parents is concerned it is negatively correlated with goal setting of male adolescents which means that when parents are more behaviourally involved there is found to be less Goal setting among male adolescents.

Table 3: Coefficient of Correlation between Goal Setting among Female adolescents and Dimensions of Parental Involvement

Variables	Category	N	R	Sig./Not Sig.
Goal Setting and Personal Involvement	Female adolescents	232	0.38	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Cognitive Stimulation	Female Adolescents	232	0.38	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Behaviour Involvement	Female Adolescents	232	-0.27	Sig. at .01
Goal Setting and Cognitive Behaviour	Female Adolescents	232	0.14	Sig. at .05

Table 3 shows that

- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.38 which is significant at 0.01 level. Table further shows that there exists a positive relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.38 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exist a positive relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement is -0.27 which is significant at 0.01 level which further shows that there exist negative relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- The coefficient of correlation between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement is 0.14 which is significant at 0.05 level which shows that there exist positive relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

Therefore hypothesis 3 stating that “There exists significant relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement (Personal Involvement, Cognitive Stimulation, Behaviour Involvement and Cognitive Behaviour),” stands accepted.

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The findings of the study further indicate that parents personal involvement, their cognitive stimulation to adolescents thoughts and feelings and cognitive behaviour is positively correlated with goal setting of female adolescents which means that more personal involvement, cognitive stimulation and cognitive behaviour leads to more goal setting of female adolescents; as far as the behaviour involvement of parents is concerned it is negatively correlated with goal setting of female adolescents which shows that where there is more behaviour involvement there is less goal setting among female adolescents.

IV. FINDINGS

1. Findings of the correlational analysis between the variable Goal Setting among adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement

- (a) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (b) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (c) There exists a significant negative relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (d) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

2. Findings of the correlational analysis between the variable Goal Setting among male adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement

- (a) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (b) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (c) There exists a significant negative relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (d) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among male adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

3. Findings of the correlational analysis between the variable Goal Setting among female adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement

- (a) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Personal Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (b) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Cognitive Stimulation dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (c) There exists a significant negative relationship between Goal Setting among female adolescents and Behaviour Involvement dimension of Parental Involvement.
- (d) There exists a significant positive relationship between Goal setting among female adolescents and Cognitive Behaviour dimension of Parental Involvement.

V. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

A study painting will not whole in itself unless and till the research findings have a few applicability or realistic implications. The findings of the present look at may be used as guidelines to encourage parental involvement in setting of goals, top-rated motivation amongst young people and academic overall performance of the teens. The present take a look at reveals sizable fine relationship among goal setting amongst adolescents and dimensions of Parental Involvement which indicates discern's personal involvement, their cognitive behaviour and cognitive stimulation performs an essential function in placing of educational and vocational goals in their youngsters. The existing study can be useful for parents to manual their child in deciding on proper subject or profession as they involve themselves in education of their children and offer appropriate platform and congenial environment at home that might assist their wards in placing sensible, meaningful, measurable and handy goals. As Behaviour Involvement of Parental Involvement is concerned it indicates negative but vast courting with goal setting which courses the mother and father that their children do now not like they could come to high school to satisfy their teachers and attend parent teacher meetings; it is very a good deal herbal at this level as we realize at this stage a teen is growing intellectually, emotionally and socially. They need independence and prefer much less interference especially in public. The study might have practical implication for adolescents in setting of educational and vocational goals to reap fulfillment.

The present endeavour additionally reveals extensive relationship among goal setting amongst male children and dimensions of Parental Involvement i.e. private, Cognitive Behaviour and Cognitive Stimulation. The findings also indicates that parents need

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to more involve themselves within the education in their male youngsters as adolescent stage is a crucial one their right involvement and steering positioned their children on proper course and makes their future brilliant and relaxed. The current research might assist the parents to recognize early life is the period of independence and transferring toward maturity so they should admire that feeling of male children. The result of the look at similarly explores that there's enormous courting between goals setting among female adolescents and Personal, Cognitive Stimulation and Cognitive Behaviour dimensions of Parental Involvement. Parental involvement is great for setting of goals for girl teens. The observe study would additionally assist within the feel that female training and career is critical in these days' situation so, parent ought to contain themselves in schooling of their female toddler so they can face hard stages and demanding situations of the existence. The observe study will also guides the mother and father and instructors to apprehend what the female at this level needs and they need to apprehend their feelings as behaviour involvement shows poor however big courting with goal setting. The observe study will also helpful for college students or youngsters to realize the importance of goals and to set significant, purposeful and long time goals for achievement in academic and vocational field.

VI. CONCLUSION

Under the light of above discussion and analysis the investigator come to the conclusion that parents involvement have great impact on educational and vocational goal setting of adolescents whether they are male adolescents or female adolescents. Parents' personal involvement, cognitive behavior, motivation, cognitive stimulation provided by them as well as their involvement in academic activities or in school programmes assists their children in setting goals.

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